

THE NAKHCHIVAN INDUSTRIAL PARK AND ITS ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT**Nagiyev Kazim***PhD in Economics**Nakhchivan State University**Institute of Natural Resources*<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9936-3295>**Abstract**

At the present stage, industrial parks play an important role in stimulating regional economic development and increasing employment levels. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the establishment of industrial zones as an integral part of targeted measures aimed at accelerating the development of the non-oil sector in our country. In this regard, the Nakhchivan Industrial Park, established in 2024, can be considered a strategic initiative aimed at strengthening the industrial potential of the autonomous republic. This article examines the objectives, sectoral structure, investment incentives, and potential socio-economic impacts of the industrial park. The research findings indicate that the Nakhchivan Industrial Park will play a significant role in enhancing regional economic sustainability, creating new jobs, and expanding export-oriented production.

Keywords: industry, production, regional development, industrial park, non-oil sector

Introduction

At the modern stage, industry, as one of the main branches of material production, plays a leading role due to the volume and importance of the goods it produces. Industry is a field of material production that, by efficiently using natural resources, produces goods for personal consumption as well as technical and industrial use. It primarily includes sectors such as fuel and energy, mechanical engineering, chemistry, light industry, food production, and others [4 p.7].

In modern times, regional economic development has become one of the main priorities of economic policy in many developing countries. By providing centralized infrastructure, fiscal incentives, and institutional support mechanisms, industrial parks play an important role in increasing industrial competitiveness. In our country, industrial parks are widely implemented to develop the non-oil sector. The establishment of the Nakhchivan Industrial Park contributes to the formation of a specialized industrial zone in the region, creating favorable conditions for expanding production capacity, increasing employment, and enhancing economic self-sufficiency in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Main Part

December 5, 2024, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, signed a decree on the establishment of the Nakhchivan Industrial Park in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. This project, which is an important component of the economic policy aimed at developing the non-oil industry in Azerbaijan, will make a significant contribution to the sustainable socio-economic development of the region. The newly established industrial park will play an important role in strengthening the industrial potential of the autonomous republic, promoting entrepreneurship, applying modern technologies, producing competitive products for domestic and foreign markets, creating new jobs, and ensuring economic growth.

A land area of 310 hectares has been allocated for the Nakhchivan Industrial Park in the southwestern part

of Nakhchivan city, on the left side of the Nakhchivan–Sadarak highway. The area has access to international road and railway networks, making it a strategically important location.

The industrial park will create favorable conditions for the development of competitive industrial production based on innovative and high technologies, strengthen industrial potential, support entrepreneurship, create new jobs, and ensure economic growth in the autonomous republic.

The main priority sectors of the Nakhchivan Industrial Park include the chemical industry, food industry, waste processing, ferrous and non-ferrous metal processing, construction materials production, machinery and equipment manufacturing, renewable energy production, furniture, textiles, clothing, leather production, packaging, and paper products manufacturing. Tax and customs incentives for residents, along with ready infrastructure, will increase the attractiveness of the investment environment. The park will contribute to the diversification of the regional economy and the development of industrial sectors, enabling the creation of value-added production and increasing the competitiveness of industrial products. One of the key socio-economic impacts of the park is job creation. Enterprises operating within the park will expand employment opportunities in the region, positively influencing the labor market.

Conclusion

The establishment of the Nakhchivan Industrial Park is an important step in regional development as part of targeted measures aimed at accelerating the development of the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan. The park is being developed in line with international industrial zone practices and has the potential to play a strategic role in the regional economic development of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

By stimulating industrial diversification, the park can contribute to increased employment, attraction of investments, and strengthening of economic sustainability. This project will significantly enhance the industrial potential of the region, promote entrepreneurship,

support the production of competitive goods for domestic and foreign markets, create new jobs, increase employment levels, and ensure sustainable socio-economic development.

References

1. Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan – <https://economy.gov.az>
2. Economic Zones Development Agency – <https://economiczones.gov.az>
3. Ahmadov N. Priorities of Nakhchivan Economy: Economic Growth and Dynamic Development. Baku, Sabah, 2008, 452 p.
4. Nagiyev K. Industry and its development stages. Danish Scientific Journal, Copenhagen, Denmark, No. 96, 2025, pp. 7–9. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15553059